

INTERFACIAL AND INTERNAL STRESS TRANSFER IN CARBON NANOTUBE BASED NANOCOMPOSITES

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Keywords: Carbon nanotubes, Nanocomposites, Micromechanics, Raman spectroscopy

ABSTRACT

This study is concerned with structure-property relationships in different types of carbon nanotubes (CNTs), in particular investigating both interfacial and internal stress transfer for CNTs in nanocomposites. The shift of position and width of the G'-Raman band for single-walled CNTs (SWNTs) and multi-walled CNTs (MWNTs) in an epoxy matrix was used to monitor stress transfer between the nanotubes and an epoxy matrix in nanocomposites. A theory has been developed to simulate this behaviour and determine the stress transfer efficiency parameter, (k_i) for the MWNTs. It is demonstrated that MWNTs give inferior reinforcement to SWNTs as a result of slippage between the walls giving rise to poor internal stress transfer in the MWNTs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) possess extremely high values of modulus (~1 TPa) and strength (~120 GPa), that have prompted many scientists to use them as reinforcements in composite materials. On the other hand, epoxy resins are known for their high tensile strength, modulus and adhesion, and their ability to withstand high temperature, complete with corrosion and chemical resistance. Due to the good mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties of nanocomposites made from CNTs and epoxy resins, there is a wide range of useful and potential applications focussing on their use as reinforcements in structural materials, coatings, or integrated constituents in multifunctional materials.

The surface and interface play an important role in controlling the properties of a broad range of composite materials including CNTs/epoxy nanocomposites. The development of improved high performance polymer composites based on CNTs can only be achieved by simultaneously optimizing the CNT aspect ratio, dispersion, packing, bonding between the epoxy and CNTs at the interface, inter-wall sliding within CNTs under tension and reduced polymer shrinkage during processing. Raman spectroscopy can be used to characterize the deformation behaviour of carbon nanotubes in composites. Evidence of stress transfer between the matrix and the carbon nanotubes can be observed from the stress induced shifts of the Raman bands [1].

Recently, researchers have shown interest in following stress transfer from the positions of the stress sensitive G', G, and D bands as well as the intensities of the radial breathing modes (RBM) band to detect the interface damage of SWNT bundles [2], double-wall nanotubes [3] and MWNTs in epoxy nanocomposites [1]. Applying external strains that disturb the electronic structure of carbon nanotubes in epoxy nanocomposites causes shifts in their Raman peak positions (G, D and G') as well as the linewidths and the intensities of RBM (radial breathing modes). Far less attention has been paid, however, to the corresponding full-width half maximum (FWHM) changes in the Raman peaks.

The aim of this study was to determine and evaluate the degree of the interface damage of nanotube interactions with epoxy polymers detected from G'-frequency shifts and the corresponding changes in the full-width half maximum (FWHM). The Raman response of SWNTs and MWNTs in epoxy nanocomposites during tensile deformation process is simulated. The similarities and differences between SWNTs and MWNTs in epoxy nanocomposites were investigated in detail.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Carbon nanotubes

The SWNTs (HiPco material) were used as-received from Carbon Nanotechnologies, Inc., of Houston, USA. The MWNTs used in this study were synthesized using a chemical vapour deposition (CVD) process adapted from Singh et al [4]. A solution of 5 wt% ferrocene in toluene was injected at a rate of 0.04 ml/min into an argon gas stream pre-heated to 200 °C and flowing at 100 ml/min. The reactants were carried into the reaction zone which was at 760 °C, where the nanotubes were grown on a quartz surface. The reaction time was 4 h, after which the reactor was cooled to room temperature under argon and the MWNTs harvested from the growth substrates.

The microstructures of SWNTs and MWNTs were characterised by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a Philips CM200 TEM with a tungsten filament operated at 200 kV.

2.2 Nanocomposite preparation

The matrix system used in this study was a low viscosity epoxy resin supplied by Huntsman Co. It consists of Araldite LY5052 as an epoxy phenol novolak resin and Aradur 5052 CH as a liquid polyamine hardener with a weight mixing ratio of 100:38 respectively. The MWNTs were used as-made and the SWNTs as-received.

An extensive mixing procedure was used to ensure good dispersion of the CNTs. They were suspended in ethanol (17 g) using an ultrasonic bath for 1.5 h. The resin (100 parts by weight, 100 g) of was then added to the mixture, which was sonicated for a further 4 h. For homogenization, the mixture was stirred at room temperature using a mechanical stirrer for two days, followed by sonication in the bath for 8 h. In order to remove ethanol residues, the mixture was stirred mechanically (100 rpm, 85°C) then at 50°C for 7 h and 12 h respectively. For de-gassing, the mixture was left in a thermostatted vacuum oven (at 70 °C for 30 min). The hardener (19 parts by weight) was added, after the mixture was cooled to room temperature, and stirred mechanically for 10 min. The mixture was put into a vacuum oven to de-gas for a further 15 min. For Raman testing, samples were prepared by carefully casting the mixture into a stainless steel square mould (160 × 160 × 3 mm).

The nanocomposites were then cured at 100 °C for 2 h, removed immediately from the oven and left to cool at room temperature. For Raman investigations and thermo-mechanical measurements the nanocomposite samples were cut into rectangular specimens. The nanocomposite samples were prepared for comparative purposes, with concentrations of SWNTs and MWNTs of 0.1 wt%.

2.3 Raman Spectroscopy and in-situ deformation

The Raman spectra of the nanocarbon powders and nanocarbon/epoxy nanocomposites were obtained at room temperature using a Renishaw Raman imaging microscope system 1000 with an Olympus BHM microscope. A notch (Rayleigh line rejection) filter with a limit of 100 cm⁻¹ was used. An excitation frequency of 633 nm (1.96 eV) polarized laser excitation lines and a back-scattering geometry was used to collect the Raman signals without the use of a polarization analyser.

A fixed laser power was employed with maximum value of 1.20 mW and focused on to a spot size of about 1 μm in diameter with an MD plan 50× objective lens (numerical aperture 0.75). Spectra were acquired in the range 2500-2800 cm⁻¹ and over 100-3000 cm⁻¹ (Stokes shift) with the continuous extended grating mode. The spectra collection was repeated a number of times to reduce the signal noise. All the Raman band spectra were analyzed by Lorentzian routines. For the same batch of material, the Raman spectra are presented as the average of spectra from three different specimens.

For deformation, the rectangular specimens with dimensions of 61 mm length, 14 mm width, and 3 mm thickness were loaded axially using a four-point bending rig, which was located on the Raman microscope stage. The composite beams were deformed step-by-step in ~0.1 % strain intervals, determined from strain gauges, with a gauge factor of 2.09 attached to the surface by cyanoacrylate adhesive. The conditions for tensile deformation of CNT/epoxy nanocomposites were loading of the nanocomposites up to 1.5 % strain with several Raman spectra obtained at each strain level.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The morphology of the CNTs

Figures 1 show TEM images of the SWNTs and MWNTs. In general, most of the HiPco SWNTs consist of bundles of well-aligned carbon filaments shown by TEM 40 ± 25 nm in size and accompanied by numerous iron particles of around 3 - 4 nm in diameter. The diameters of the SWNTs, deduced from the Raman wavenumber of the RBM modes, were mostly in the range 0.6 - 1.7 nm and with an average diameter of 1.02 ± 0.22 nm. There were also residual catalyst particles in the bundles of SWNTs.

The morphology of the MWNTs was first observed by scanning electron microscopy which showed bundles of entangled tubes, 225 ± 85 μm in length. Most of the MWNTs have irregular curved and entangled tubular structures that are hollow inside. They were shown by TEM to have 61 ± 24 nm and 9 ± 3 nm outer and inner diameters, respectively, and accompanied by numerous iron particles around 72 ± 37 nm in length and 13 ± 5 nm in diameter. Some encapsulated particles and other particles attached to the nanotube walls were observed for the MWNTs. Lattice fringes from the graphene layers with a 0.33 nm spacing can be seen in the inset in the TEM image in Figure 1(d).

Figure 1: TEM image of the CNT powders at different magnifications with scale bars for as-received SWNTs (a) 100nm, (b) 20 nm , and for as-grown MWNTs (c) 100 nm, (d) 5 nm with an inset image of the inner layers of single MWNT nanotube.

3.2 Raman spectra of CNTs in epoxy nanocomposites

Figure 2 shows the Raman spectra of the hot-cured epoxy resin, the SWNTs and MWNTs and their epoxy composites excited using a 633 nm (He-Ne) laser. The high relative intensities of the Raman bands of all the CNTs, even at 0.1 wt% loading, compared to the epoxy bands in the nanocomposites are due to the strong resonance Raman scattering from the CNTs.

Figures 2(b) and 2(d) compare the G'-bands of the SWNTs and MWNTs either in the powder form or in their epoxy composites in the range $2500\text{-}2800$ cm^{-1} . The G'-bands of SWNTs and MWNTs are still well-defined but their frequency is upshifted by about 10 cm^{-1} in the composites. This may be the

result of the generation of internal residual compressive stresses induced during the curing shrinkage, as well as thermal shrinkage during cooling from the cure temperature [5].

Figure 2: (a) and (c) Raman spectra of the epoxy resin, the SWNTs and MWNTs respectively and hot-cured CNT/epoxy nanocomposites in the range 1000-3000 cm^{-1} excited using 633 nm (He-Ne) laser. (b) and (d) G'-Raman spectra of SWNT and MWNT powder and hot-cured SWNT/epoxy nanocomposites in the range 2500-2800 cm^{-1} excited using the 633 nm (He-Ne) laser.

3.3 Effect of deformation upon the Raman spectra of CNT/epoxy nanocomposites

Figure 3(a) shows the shift of G'-band frequencies of the SWNTs and MWNTs in the epoxy composites during tensile deformation up to 1.5% strain and it can be seen that there is a general downshift of the G'-band. The initial shift rate was found to be $-14.1 \pm 3.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ strain for the SWNTs compared with a much lower value of $-3.4 \pm 1.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ strain for the MWNTs in the same resin cured under the same conditions.

Figure 3(b) shows the G' band widths (full width at half maximum, FWHM) plotted as a function of strain for the two CNT/epoxy composites. There is a striking difference between the two CNT materials in that the G' band widths of the SWNTs increase (broadening) while those of MWNTs decrease (narrowing) with tensile strain. There are similarities between the broadening behaviour of the G' band widths in this study and the G band widths described by Kumar et al [6]. The authors assumed that the strain-induced broadening observed in their semiconducting SWNTs is attributed to inhomogeneous deformation, which is expected if the strain is not uniformly distributed between the nanotubes. This would not, however, explain the anomalous band narrowing behaviour of the MWNTs. This is the subject of this present study.

Figure 3: (a) The shift of the G'-band position and (b) the change of widths of the G'-band (FWHM) for hot cured SWNT and MWNT/epoxy composites up to 1.5 % maximum loading strain fitted to one Lorentzian peak (excited using a 633 nm (He-Ne) laser).

It has been established that the G'-band shift rate is related to the effective Young's modulus, E_{eff} , of the CNTs in a composite [7]. The initial shift rate of $S(0) = -14.1 \pm 3.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ strain for the SWNTs is over four times higher than $S(0)$ for the MWNTs at the same loading of nanotubes (0.1 wt%) in the same epoxy resin prepared in an identical way. This implies that the E_{eff} of the SWNTs is over four times higher than that of the MWNTs [6]. Consideration will now be given to why this is the case.

4 INTERFACIAL STRESS TRANSFER

4.1 SWNT/epoxy nanocomposites

Considerable work has been done using Raman spectroscopy to investigate the deformation of SWNTs in SWNT/polymer composites to probe degradation of the interface between the polymers and nanotubes [8], to measure the interfacial shear strength of the SWNT-matrix interface [2] and to map the strain fields around fibres in a glass fibre-reinforced polymer composite [9,10]. This has been undertaken using the shift of the D-, G-, G'- Raman band frequencies. The G'-Raman band has the highest shift rate per unit strain which for individual isolated SWNTs can be as large as $-40 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ strain [11] which approaches the value of the 2D band shift rate of $-60 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ strain for graphene [12]. In the nanocomposites $S(0)$ is significantly lower and ranges from -1.3 to $-15 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ strain. This wide range has been attributed to the SWNT bundle size, dispersion of the nanotubes, variations in nanotube orientation, as well as differences in interfacial adhesion to the matrix [13]. Our value of band shift rate, at the top of this range, implies that in our nanocomposites there is a good dispersion of SWNTs with strong interfacial adhesion to the matrix.

It has been demonstrated that the frequency of the G'-peak depends on the tube diameter of the isolated SWNTs [14] through:

$$\omega_{G'} = \omega_{G'_0} - \left(\frac{35.4}{D} \right) \quad (1)$$

where ω_{G_0} is the frequency G`-band in graphene (cm^{-1}) that is laser energy dependent and D is the diameter (nm) of the individual tubes in the MWNTs and SWNTs. The SWNT powder has a value of ω_{G_0} of $2602 \pm 6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which yields a value for monolayer graphene at the laser wavelength used of $\omega_{G_0} = 2637 \pm 6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is close to the accepted value [14].

The G' band shift rate $S(0)$ is defined as

$$S(0) = d\omega_{G'} / d\varepsilon \quad (2)$$

where ε is the strain in the nanocomposite. Hence at a given strain ε the value frequency of the Raman G' band will be

$$\omega_{G'_{\text{CNT}}} = \omega_{G_0} + S(0)\varepsilon - \left(\frac{35.4}{D} \right) \quad (3)$$

for a SWNT of diameter D . The dashed line in Figure 3(a) corresponds to this equation plotted for the SWNT nanocomposite with $S(0) = -14.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ strain. It can be seen in Figure 3(a) that the experimental data deviate from the dashed line above around 0.5% strain due probably to slippage at the SWNT-matrix interface [8]. It should also be noted that Figure 3(b) shows that the G' band for the SWNTs undergoes broadening above around 0.5% strain which is similar to the behaviour of graphene monolayers for which the G'(2D) band undergoes broadening with strain [14] but there could again be contributions from slippage and local strain differences in the nanocomposites.

4.2 MWNT/epoxy nanocomposites

In view of the lower G' Raman band shift rate for the MWNTs an exercise has been undertaken to model their deformation in nanocomposites. It is assumed that the SWNTs and MWNTs have an identical dispersion and the strength of the nanotube-matrix interface is the same. The only difference is that in the MWNTs stress transfer to the inner walls has to take place by shear between the different graphene layers. The model chosen based upon that employed earlier for DWNTs [3] and is shown in Figure 4. The SWNTs ($n = 1$) are described by a (5, 5) layer and the family of ten coaxial commensurate tubes for MWNTs which it can be presented by (5*n*, 5*n*), (5*n*-1, 5*n*-1), (5*n*-2, 5*n*-2),....., (5*n*-9, 5*n*-9) for the outermost wall, the ninth wall, the eighth wall,....., and the innermost wall, respectively. The separation between individual walls in MWNTs is constant (~0.35 nm) for this family in tubes. The outermost wall (5*n*, 5*n*) is in contact directly with the epoxy polymer matrix. The relationship between the transmittance of light $T\%$ and the number of graphene layers has been widely investigated where monolayer graphene is found to transmit about 97.7% of visible white light [15].

Through this stress transfer model for MWNTs the Raman spectra of the stress-induced shift rate of the G`-band in carbon nanotubes in epoxy composites have been simulated to estimate the load transfer efficiency of any nanotubes in the (5*n*, 5*n*) family where n is an integer. The G'-band was chosen because it has a higher strain sensitivity compared with the Raman first order band, particularly at low levels of strain. All calculations were performed on computational software programs Mathematica 8 and OriginPro 8.5.

If there is perfect stress transfer between the individual layers in the MWNTs then it would be expect that during deformation there would be the same band shift rate between each layer of $S(0)$. If the stress transfer is not perfect and the stress transfer efficiency can be described by a factor k_i [3,16] then it would be expected that $S(0)$ would be reduced by a factor of k_i for each successive layer such that that measured band shift rate for the MWNTs would be lower than that for the equivalent SWNTs. The analysis outlined below explains how this may be modelled.

The individual components of the G'-band from the family of the nanotubes and the resultant overall G' band are presented in Figure 5. In order to know the appropriate value of the stress transfer efficiency parameters, k_i , for the experimental shift of the Raman G' bands, the value of the stress transfer efficiency parameters, k_i were changed between zero and one in steps of 0.1 as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 4: The depicted geometry for MWNTs where $n=10$. The outermost wall (50, 50) is in contact directly with the polymer epoxy matrix.

Figure 5: The simulated Raman spectrum for G' bands for MWNTs in MWNT/epoxy nanocomposites at 0 % strain.

The calculations of the resulting line shapes of the G'-peak induced stresses, for 10 layers, yielding a best fit with a shear transfer efficiency parameter, ($k_i \approx 0.7$). Some authors [3,16] have speculated that the limiting cases for the shear transfer efficiency parameter corresponding to perfect and no shear transfer (full slip) are $k_i = 1.0$ and $k_i = 0$, respectively as shown in Figure 6. The reason for this could be attributed to the imperfect interface bonding between layers, therefore the shear stress decreases

steadily as the number of layers increases. Consequently, as the load is taken mainly by the outside layer and the inner layers offer decreasing reinforcement.

Figure 6: The experimental shift of the Raman G' bands positions (solid navy hexagons) and their corresponding model simulation (solid green down triangles) as a function of strain from 0 to 1.5% for hot-cured 0.1wt% MWNT/epoxy nanocomposites and the different values of the stress transfer efficiency parameters, k_i as a function of strain from 0 to 1.5% for hot-cured 0.1wt% MWNT/epoxy nanocomposites.

Comparisons between the experimental and simulated of the G' -bands downshifts are presented in Figure 7(a). It is observed that the G' band shifts approximately linearly and suggest that good bonding between the MWNTs and epoxy matrix. However, on increasing the tensile strain the shift becomes non-linear. For MWNTs/epoxy composites, the most striking result to emerge from Figure 7(b) is that the narrowing of G' -band up to 1.5% strain found in both the experimental and simulated data. This is probably due to the outer walls being more highly strained than the inner walls, leading to larger band shifts for the outer walls components of the G' band spectrum (Figure 5).

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper has investigated the central importance of stress transfer Raman studies in epoxy composites reinforced with the CNTs (SWNTs and MWNTs) to elucidate the reinforcing ability of the CNTs in an epoxy matrix. It was undertaken to assess the stress transfer efficiency at the CNT/epoxy interface and between the inner walls of the CNTs with tensile deformation. Optimized conditions were applied to produce MWNTs with a high yield, high aspect ratio and well-defined G' Raman peak MWNTs. The most obvious finding to be drawn from the present paper is that the reinforcement of the epoxy resin with different CNTs would be useful. The stress-induced Raman shifts in the nanocomposites have been shown to be controlled by the number of carbon nanolayers. A theory has been developed to determine and simulate the stress transfer efficiency parameter, (k_i) for MWNTs. Overall the highest effective Young's modulus and best reinforcement is found for the SWNTs but they undergo interfacial slippage above around 0.5% strain. The MWNTs have a lower effective Young's modulus as a result of slippage between the internal layers of the CNTs but they appear to show better interfacial stress transfer with the matrix than the SWNTs.

Figure 7 (a) Experimental shift of the Raman G` bands positions and their corresponding model simulation and (b) Experimental shift of the Raman G` bands widths (FWHM) and their corresponding model simulation as a function of strain from 0 to 1.5 % for the hot cured 0.1 wt % MWNT/epoxy nanocomposite, where $k_i \approx 0.7$ for the simulated data.

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